

CSR At Work: How Training, Stability, And Diversity Shape Employee Responses

Pilar Blaya-Hernandez¹, Rafael Curras-Perez²

^{1,2}University of Valencia, Spain

ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 27 May 2025	This study analyses the influence of CSR internal work practices on employees. The fieldwork was conducted through an online questionnaire answered by more than 1,200 employees in organizations in Spain. The analysis model used was structural equation model (SEM) based on the package of Partial Least Square. The empirical research revealed that promoting training and development, job stability, and equality and team diversity have a direct, positive and significant impact on individuals' behaviors and attitudes, which is manifested in greater motivation, feelings of organizational identification and job satisfaction. Consequently, organizations are encouraged to adopt or reinforce these beneficial practices, and to replicate this research in their own context.
Corresponding Author: Rafael Curras-Perez	
KEYWORDS: Corporate Social Responsibility, employees, job satisfaction	

I. INTRODUCTION

The current global scenario, identified as BANI (Cascio, 2020), is characterized as being brittle, anxious, nonlinear, and incomprehensible, all of which cause rapid changes in the business environment. Various international organizations (e.g., UN, OECD, EU) have been encouraging companies for decades to get involved in improving social conditions and to implement corporate social responsibility (CSR) strategies (Celma et al., 2018). In its Green Paper (European Union, 2001), the European Commission defined CSR as a concept whereby companies integrate social and environmental concerns in their business operations and in their interaction with their stakeholders on a voluntary basis. CSR is, therefore, an evolving multidimensional concept that has attracted the attention of many scholars (Carroll, 2021; Turker, 2009; Glavas & Kelley, 2014).

Human capital management is a critical and strategic issue for all organizations (Green et al, 2006; Kramar, 2022). The previous literature argues that employees play a key role in business success and failure (Del-Castillo-Feito et al., 2022). When companies prioritize the well-being and satisfaction of their employees, they are more likely to achieve their goals (Kramar, 2013). Research on the effects and experiences of CSR on individuals is gaining importance (Rupp & Mallory, 2015) although more analysis and understanding are needed (Del-Castillo-Feito et al., 2022; Farid et al., 2019). In the business field, it is important to identify what work practices can be developed by companies to positively impact on, motivate and retain their staff.

However, little research has focused on workers as beneficiaries of CSR internal work practices, and direct employees' perceptions in this regard.

Previous studies examining the relationship between CSR and human resources have focused on employees' general perceptions of companies' behaviors, on their participation in CSR activities, on the effects on them of their perceptions of the company's external CSR or on the potential for attracting talent (Brammer et al., 2007; Glavas, 2016; Story & Castanheira, 2019). It has been shown that internal CSR activities generate positive employee behaviors towards companies, leading to better work performance.

In addition, studies in this field are usually based on the content of business re-ports or on the opinions of managers and multinational companies (Del-Castillo-Feito et al., 2022; Barrena-Martínez et al. 2016; Tsourvakas & Yfantidou, 2018). Few analyses have been based on the perceptions of employees of smaller companies despite the presence, and importance of SMEs in the business fabric.

The present study aims to empirically analyze the impact of employees' perceptions from several types of Spain-based organizations. Specifically, the research analyses whether voluntary business practices such as training and development of personnel, job stability and support for equality and diversity, create favorable employ-ee responses, such as motivation, organizational identification and overall job satisfaction.

II. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

A. Corporate Social Responsibility as a company strategy and its labour dimension

Companies began to progressively integrate CSR practices almost two decades ago, relying on international instruments that inspire, promote and make visible the improvement of working conditions at a global level (GRI, SGE 21, ISO 26000:2010). All of them articulate business activities around a series of areas of action focused on environmental, social and governance (ESG) criteria, with the aim of contributing to sustainable development.

This research supports Stakeholder Theory (Freeman, 1984), which proposes that the systematic management of stakeholder interests is critical to the success of any company. This study assumes the findings of previous investigations which argued that contextual differences condition the approach and implementation of CSR and personnel management models in companies in each country (Díaz-Carrión et al., 2018; Matten & Moon, 2008).

Employees are fundamental stakeholders of any organization (Azim et al., 2014). Previous studies (Celma et al., 2018; Del-Castillo-Feito et al., 2022; Barrena-Martínez et al. 2016) have typically identified a series of socially responsible labor policies around which they structure practices with the following content: employment, selection and hiring; management of labor relations; occupational hygiene, health and safety; training and development; equality, diversity and inclusion; compensation and remuneration; and other working conditions.

B. Socially responsible business practices and their direct impact on organisations' employees.

The promotion of training and professional development, support for job stability and guarantees of equality and diversity. Companies generally have a certain margin of maneuver to improve the working conditions of their employees, such as the areas highlighted below. Firstly, it is understood that training and development practices are company initiatives that promote training, improve skills and aid their employees' professional growth, in a way that enhances their evolution, autonomy, continuous improvement and the development of a career within the company (Díaz-Carrión et al., 2018; Barrena-Martínez et al. 2017; Tang et al., 2023). Secondly, according to ISO 26000:2010, job stability has been described as the job security provided by companies (ISO, 2010). Several studies describe long-term employment as a specific interest and need of the members of organizations (Järlström et al., 2018). Thirdly, the promotion of equality and diversity involves actions that provide all employees with the same opportunities and rights, regardless of gender, age, nationality or any other characteristic, condition or personal situation (Díaz-Carrión et al., 2020). Some authors refer to these practices as procedural justice, in the sense of applying equity in the organization's processes and decisions (Brammer et al., 2007). Finally, diversity has been conceived

as the presence of differences between members of a social unit (Jackson et al., 1995).

The scientific literature shows that CSR is considered to influence individual employees' attitudes and behaviors (De Roeck et al., 2014; Zhou et al., 2017). Several empirical studies have revealed that specific workplace-based CSR initiatives have a significant influence on staff engagement (Albdour & Altarawneh, 2012; Ibrahim et al., 2014).

Motivation, organizational identification and job satisfaction. Motivation has been extensively studied [32]. It can be described as the driving force within individuals that prompts them to initiate and maintain goal-directed performance (Clark, 2003). Organizational identification relates to the perceived oneness with an organization and the experience of the organization's successes and failures as one's own (Mael & Ashforth, 1992). This approach is based on social identity theory (Brammer et al., 2007; Ashforth & Mael, 1989), which proposes that people seek to define their identities, in part, by their membership of certain social groups or categories. Several studies have shown that internal employee-focused CSR practices enhance their level of identification with companies, considering that work is a fundamental part of people's lives (De Roeck et al., 2014; Brammer et al., 2015; Hong & Roh, 2024). Finally, job satisfaction has been defined as pleasant or well-intentioned emotional state that results from the general appreciation of one's own work or work experiences (Locke, 1976), and the degree to which people like their work (Spector, 1997). Several studies have identified CSR as having a direct and positive influence on satisfaction (De Roeck et al., 2014; Glavas & Kelley, 2014; Loor-Zambrano et al., 2020).

C. Proposed model

Three socially responsible work practices were selected for this research: training and development, job stability and equality and diversity measures. Motivation, identification with the organization and job satisfaction were selected as dependent variables (Figure 1). The structural model proposes the existence and significance of direct and positive causal relationships between the aforementioned practices and behaviors.

Figure 1. Theoretical model

Thus, we test the following hypotheses:

H1abc. Practices that support training and professional development influence (a) work motivation, (b) identification with the organization and (c) job satisfaction.

H2abc. Practices that promote job stability influence (a) work motivation, (b) identification with the organization and (c) job satisfaction.

H3abc. Practices that promote equality and diversity influence (a) work motivation, (b) identification with the organization and (c) job satisfaction.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Design and fieldwork

To carry out a homogeneous analysis, facilitate comparability and consistent treatment, the present survey was limited to adults who reside and work in Spain. This approach is in accordance with institutional theory and other research which state that generalization denies the national peculiarities of CSR (Díaz-Carrión et al., 2018; Matten & Moon, 2008; Miethlich et al., 2023].

The online survey was conducted in Spring 2023. Following pertinent revisions and the filtering of the responses, the final sample consisted of 1,244 complete and valid answers. The profile of the participants was very balanced and representative of the Spanish working population: 51.53% men and 48.07% women; 78% in non-managerial positions; 18.5% middle management and 7.3% senior managers; 41.7% millennials and later, 47.67% Generation X; around 42% with secondary or vocational training, and 56% with undergraduate and higher studies; 45% have salaries in line with the national average, 10% below, and 10% above.

The employing organizations reflect the current picture in Spain: more than 71% of the employees came from the private sector, 22% from the public sector and 4% from the third sector; 85.77% had headquarters in Spain; 16.4% had been in existence for up to 10 years, 15% between 11 and 20 years and 56.3% more than 20 years; 16.32% of the sample were micro-enterprises, 16.88% small enterprises, 18.09% medium-sized enterprises, and 48.7% of large companies.

B. Data collection instrument

To measure the model’s variables, a structured survey was designed that could be answered by workers in all types of organizations and sectors. The indicators were selected based on a review of previous studies in the literature (Turker, 2009; Brammer et al., 2007; Díaz-Carrión et al., 2018) and drawing on standard tools, such as the GRI standards (GRI, 2025), the SGE21 certifiable management system (Forética, 2025) and ISO 26000:2010 (ISO, 2010). The questions were adapted for contextual and idiomatic reasons, and the questionnaire was pre-tested on a small sample. The statements of the constructs analyzed in this paper reflected, on the one hand, perceptions about support for training and opportunities for career development (Turker, 2009; Loo-Zambrano et al., 2020; Kucukusta et

al., 2017; Shen & Zhu, 2011), the sense of security (e.g., it offers above-average job stability) (Del-Castillo-Feito et al., 2022; Kim et al., 2020), and the perception of commitment to equality and diversity (Turker, 2009; Del-Castillo-Feito et al., 2022; Kucukusta et al., 2017; Shen & Zhu, 2011; D’Netto & Sohal, 1999).

On the other hand, the impact on employees was captured through statements highlighting influences on motivation (such as "the attention of the organization that I perceive drives me to work as well as possible") (Turker, 2009; Green et al., 2006), and the feeling of personal identification with the organization (Mael & Ashforth, 1992 Carmeli et al., 2007; Gautam et al., 2004; Golob & Podnar, 2021). Job satisfaction was measured as a general feeling of satisfaction with the company, through a single item - how satisfied they are with their work-, in its global sense (Kim et al., 2020; D’Netto & Sohal, 1999; Golob & Podnar, 2021). Each variable was measured along a seven-point Likert-type scale, with 1 referring to total disagreement, and 7 referring to total agreement.

The estimation of the measurement model and the theoretical structure of the model was performed using partial least squares (PLS) and reflective measure specifications. The parameters were estimated with SmartPLS 4 (Sarstedt et al., 2021; Ringle et al., 2024) using the bootstrapping method, with 10,000 samples, to calculate the significance of the parameters. This technique is frequently used in empirical research on organizational practices (Ringle et al., 2020), specifically those that analyze the impact of human resource management practices on staff attitudes and behaviors. All scales obtained good indicators of reliability, convergent validity, and discriminant validity.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In general terms, the analysis confirmed there were direct, positive and significant relationships between the internal CSR practices and the impacts under study, although with different intensity (see Table 1). The highest path coefficient values were linked to training and development practices. The analyses carried out also reveal that both practices equality and diversity, and job stability had a substantial influence on workers. as well.

Table 1. Tests of the hypotheses

Hypothesis		b	t	f ₂	95% CI	
					2.5 %	97.5 %
H1a.	Training development	& ->	0.50 *	16.43	0.34	0.44 0.56
	Motivation					
H1b.	Training development	& ->	0.38 *	11.38	0.16	0.31 0.44
	Identification					
H1c.	Training development	& ->	0.36 *	11.69	0.14	0.30 0.42
	Job					

Hypothesis	b	t	f ₂	95% CI	
				2.5 %	97.5 %
satisfaction					
H2a. Job stability ->	0.20	6.80*	0.05	0.14	0.26
Motivation					
H2b. Job stability ->	0.22	6.09*	0.05	0.15	0.29
Identification					
H2c. Job stability -> Job satisfaction	0.26	7.42*	0.07	0.19	0.33
H3a. Equality & diversity -> Motivation					
H3a. Equality & diversity	0.20	6.38*	0.05	0.14	0.26
H3b. Equality & diversity -> Identification					
H3b. Equality & diversity	0.26	6.50*	0.06	0.18	0.34
H3c. Equality & diversity -> Job satisfaction					
H3c. Equality & diversity	0.23	6.24*	0.05	0.16	0.31

*= p<0.01

The results of the fieldwork support the theory that CSR internal practices related to HR management affect organizational performance through its influence on employees' attitudes (Shen & Zhu, 2011) in the sense that employees undertake favorable behaviors due to the responsible proactivity of their employers. This is also consistent with previous research that found that, in addition to the direct impact on job satisfaction, employees felt valued by their management's commitment with them, and that employees' satisfaction with their promotion opportunities may depend on the CSR practices (Beatson et al., 2008; Karatepe & Tekinkus, 2006). In relation to proven positive impact of equality and diversity practices, it is important to remark that European Union new legislation is responding to growing sensitivity that demands more promotion of equality, diversity, and inclusion (García-Sánchez et al., 2024). Nevertheless, in a highly regulated European context, committed organizations must go beyond legal compliance (Rupp & Mallory, 2011). The framework of the study might result in certain practices being considered as acquired or minimum rights of employees. However, it has been observed that employees value the benefits of these voluntary practices, and that they stimulate attitudes conducive towards employing organizations. In the same vein, in the mentioned context of global uncertainty, the results suggest that organizations which provide a stable work environment increase their employees' satisfaction, strengthen their alignment with organizational goals and values and enhance their motivation.

Moreover, the results of the study support the theory that remarks that when employees perceive their employing entities are following socially responsible business practices and values, they feel greater identification. Similarly, the study's results may support previous research that draws on Social Exchange Theory (Blau, 1958), which proposes that when people perceive they gain mutual benefits from interactions with other individuals, groups or entities, they

develop well-disposed feelings and behaviors towards them. We can conclude that the implementation of internal CSR practices, in general, can be an opportunity for organizations to improve employees' work performance (Bizri et al., 2021).

V. CONCLUSIONS

The results of this research reveal that offering training and development, reinforcing job stability, and promoting equality and diversity could have a direct and positive impact on employees' motivation, organizational identification, and job satisfaction. The present study addresses a recent perspective in the scientific literature, that is, concrete evidence of the direct perception from a sample of more than 1,200 employees of the measures undertaken by organizations in response to their needs and interests. To appropriately assess the strategy and its effects, it is essential to use a contextual reference (Rupp & Mallory, 2011). The consistency of the model has verified the effectiveness of three lines of action that are essential for good work performance. It provides a solid basis for stating that organizations that want to encourage supportive behaviors in their employees should integrate them into their workforce management strategies. This reinforcement can contribute to successful organizational results, based on the improvement of the employee experience.

A. Managerial implications

The results lead to the conclusion that when employees are given the opportunity to train and grow professionally, they feel much more motivated, more connected to the organization and more satisfied with their work. But the resources available to companies to undertake employee-focused initiatives are limited. This study offers evidence that training programs and professional development are the most effective measures for increasing employees' motivation, organizational identification and job satisfaction. In a broader framework of action, allocating resources to developing training and development plans, implementing policies that promote equality and inclusion and ensuring a stable work environment, will promote a more satisfactory and attractive workplace for current and potential workers.

B. Limitations and future research lines

The main limitations provide avenues for future research. The homogeneous Spanish context could limit the value of the results. In this sense, discretionary CSR internal practices and their effects will vary based on different regulatory and business contexts. Therefore, voluntary measures adopted in some places will not be considered CSR practices in others, rather they will be regarded as the minimum expected. This circumstance, nonetheless, offers the opportunity to replicate the survey in other countries to identify whether the measures are, indeed, of widespread value and positive impact. Finally, further analysis will be carried out on other CSR practices, more impacts and multi-group analysis.

REFERENCES

1. Alb दौर, A.A. and Altarawneh, I.I. 2012. Corporate social responsibility and employee engagement in Jordan. *Int. J. Bus. Manag.* 7(16), 89. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ijbm.v7n16p89>
2. Ashforth, B. E. and Mael, F. 1989. Social identity theory and the organization. *Acad. Manag.* 14(1), 20-39. <https://doi.org/10.2307/258189>
3. Azim, M.T. Diyab, A.A. and Al-Sabaan, S.A. 2014. CSR, employee job attitude and behavior: Saudi bank experience. *Transylv. Rev. Adm. Sci.* 10(43), 25–47.
4. Barrena-Martínez, J. López-Fernández, M. and Romero-Fernández, P. M. 2017. Socially responsible human resource policies and practices: academic and professional validation. *Eur. Res. Manag. Bus. Econ.* 23(1), 55–61. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iiedeen.2016.05.001>
5. Barrena-Martínez, J. López-Fernández, M., and Romero-Fernández, P.M. 2016. Corporate social responsibility evolution through institutional and stakeholder perspectives. *Eur. Res. Manag. Bus. Econ.* 25(1), 8–14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.redee.2015.11.002>
6. Beatson, A. Lings, I. and Gudergan, S. P. 2008. Service staff attitudes, organisational practices and performance drivers. *J. Manag. Organ* 14 (2), 168-179. <https://doi.org/10.5172/jmo.837.14.2.168>
7. Bizri, R. Wahbi, M. and Al Jardali, H. 2021. The impact of CSR best practices on job performance: the mediating roles of affective commitment and work engagement. *J. Organ. Eff-People.* P. 8(1) 129-148. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JOEPP-01-2020-0015>
8. Blau, P. M. 1964. *Exchange and power in social life* transaction publishers: Piscataway, NJ, USA.
9. Brammer, S. He, H. and Mellahi, K. 2015. Corporate social responsibility, employee organizational identification, and creative effort: the moderating impact of corporate ability. *Group Organ. Manag.* 40(3), 323-352. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1059601114562246>
10. Brammer, S. Millington, A., and Rayton, B. 2007. The contribution of corporate social responsibility to organizational commitment. *Int. J. Hum. Resour. Manag.* 18(10), 1701-1719. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585190701570866>
11. Carmeli, A., Gilat G., and Waldman D.A. 2007. The role of perceived organizational performance in organizational identification, adjustment and job performance. *J. Manag. Stud.* 44(6), 972-992. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-6486.2007.00691.x>
12. Carroll, A. B. 2021. Corporate social responsibility: perspectives on the CSR construct’s development and future. *Bus. Soc* 60(6), 1258-1278. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00076503211001765>
13. Cascio, J. 2020. Facing the age of chaos. Medium.
14. Celma, D. Martínez-García, E. and Raya, J.M. 2018. Socially responsible HR practices and their effects on employees' wellbeing: empirical evidence from Catalonia, Spain. *Eur. Res. Manag. Bus. Econ.* 24(2), 82-89. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iiedeen.2017.12.001>
15. Clark R. E..2003. Fostering the work motivation of individuals and teams. *Perf. Imp.* 42(3), 21.29. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pfi.4930420305>
16. D’Netto, B. and Sohal, A.S. 1999. Human resource practices and workforce diversity: an empirical assessment. *Int. J. Manpow* 20(8), 530-547. <https://doi.org/10.1108/01437729910302723>
17. De Roeck, K. Marique, G. Stinglhamber, F. and Swaen, V. 2014. Understanding employees' responses to corporate social responsibility: mediating roles of overall justice and organizational identification. *Int. J. Hum. Resour. Manag.* 25, 91-112. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585192.2013.781528>
18. Del-Castillo-Feito, C. Blanco-González, A. and Hernández-Perlines, F. 2022. The impacts of socially responsible human resources management on organizational legitimacy. *Technol. Forecast. Soc. Change* 174, 121274. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2021.121274>
19. Díaz-Carrion, R. López-Fernández, M. and Romero-Fernandez, P. M. 2020. Sustainable human resource management and employee engagement: a holistic assessment instrument. *Corp. Soc. Responsib. Environ. Manag.* 27(4), 1749-1760. <https://doi.org/10.1002/csr.1921>
20. Díaz-Carrión, R. López-Fernández, M. & Romero-Fernandez, P. M. 2018. Developing a sustainable HRM system from a contextual perspective. *Corp. Soc. Responsib. Environ. Manag.* 25(6), 1143-1153. <https://doi.org/10.1002/csr.1528>
21. European Union, 2001. Green paper: promoting a European framework for corporate social responsibility. European Commission.
22. Farid, T. Iqbal, S. Ma, J. Castro-González, S. Khattak, A. and Khan, M. K. 2019. Employees’ perceptions of CSR, work engagement, and organizational citizenship behavior: the mediating effects of organizational justice. *Int J Environ Res Public Health* 16 (10), 1731. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph16101731>
23. Forética: SGE 21. Ethical and Socially Responsible Management System. Foretica.

- https://foretica.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/05/sge_21_ingles.pdf, last accessed 2024/10/25.
24. Freeman, R.E. 1984. *Strategic management: a stakeholder approach*. Pitman, Boston, MA, USA.
 25. García-Sánchez, I. M. Marín-Hernández, S. Ortiz-Martínez, E. and Aibar-Guzmán, B. 2024. Diversity, equity, and inclusion reporting in European Union companies. The role of female directors and the European regulatory framework. *Bus. Strategy Environ.* 7021-7040. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.3854>
 26. Gautam, T. Van Dick, R. and Wagner, U. 2004. Organizational identification and organizational commitment: distinct aspects of two related concepts. *Asian J. Soc. Psychol* 7(3), 301-315. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-839X.2004.00150.x>
 27. Glavas, A. and Kelley, K. 2014. The effects of perceived corporate social responsibility on employee attitudes. *Bus. Ethics Q* 24(2), 165-202. <https://doi.org/10.5840/beq20143206>
 28. Glavas, A. 2016. Corporate social responsibility and employee engagement: enabling employees to employ more of their whole selves at work. *Front. Psychol.* 7, 796. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2016.00796>
 29. Global Reporting Initiative. 2025. *Global Reporting*. <https://www.globalreporting.org/standards/download-the-standards>, last accessed 2024/10/25
 30. Golob, U. and Podnar, K. 2021. Corporate marketing and the role of internal csr in employees' life satisfaction: exploring the relationship between work and non-work domains. *J. Bus. Res.* 131, 664-672. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2021.01.048>
 31. Green, K. W. Wu, C. Whitten, D. and Medlin, B. 2006. The impact of strategic human resource management on firm performance and HR professionals' work attitude and work performance. *Int. J. Hum. Resour. Manag.* 17(4), 559-579. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585190600581279>
 32. Hong, Y. and Roh, T. 2024. The effect of corporate social responsibility on workplace safety: the significance of employees' moral identity. *Behav. Sci.* 14, 429. <https://doi.org/10.3390/bs14060429>
 33. Ibrahim, Y. Ahmed, M. M. and Nayel, M. T. 2024. The impact of corporate social responsibility practices on employees' engagement: the mediating role of organizational identification. *Glob. Bus. Organ. Excell* 43(2), 43-60. <https://doi.org/10.1002/joe.22212>
 34. ISO. 2010. *26000 guidance on social responsibility*. ISO: Geneva.
 35. Jackson, S.E. May, K.E. and Whitney, K. 1995. Understanding the dynamics of diversity in decision-making teams. In: *Team effectiveness and decision making in organizations*, Jossey-Bass, Guzzo, R., Salas, E. (eds), pp. 204-61, San Francisco, CA, USA.
 36. Järlström, M. Saru, E. and Vanhala, S. 2018. Sustainable Hum. Resour. Manag. with salience of stakeholders: a top management perspective. *J. Bus. Ethics* 152, 703-724. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-016-3310-8>
 37. Karatepe, O. M. and Tekinkus, M. 2006. The effects of work-family conflict, emotional exhaustion, and intrinsic motivation on job outcomes of front-line employees. *Int. J. Bank Mark.* 24(3), 173-193. <https://doi.org/10.1108/02652320610659021>
 38. Kim, J. S. Milliman, J. and Lucas, A. 2020. Effects of CSR on employee retention via identification and quality-of-work-life. *Int. J. Contemp. Hosp. Manag.* 32(3), 1163-1179. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJCHM-06-2019-0573>
 39. Kramar, R. 2013. Beyond strategic human resource management: is sustainable human resource management the next approach? *Int. J. Hum. Resour. Manag.* 25(8), 1069-1089. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585192.2013.816863>
 40. Kramar, R. 2022. Sustainable human resource management: six defining characteristics. *Asia Pac. J. Hum. Resour.* 60(1), 146-170. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1744-7941.12321>
 41. Kucukusta, D., Guillet, B. D., and Chan, H. L. 2017. The effect of CSR practices on employee affective commitment in the airline industry. *J. Qual. Assur. Hosp. Tour.* 12(3-4), 451-469. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19388160.2016.1278187>
 42. Locke, E. 1976. The nature and causes of job satisfaction. In *Handbook of industrial and organizational psychology*. pp. 1297-1349. Consulting Psychologists Press, Palo Alto, CA, USA.
 43. Loor-Zambrano, H. Santos-Roldán, L. and Palacios-Florencio, B. 2020. Corporate social responsibility, facets of employee job satisfaction and commitment: the case in Ecuador. *TQM J.* 33(2), 521-543. <https://doi.org/10.1108/TQM-01-2020-0011>
 44. Mael, F. and Ashforth, B. 1992. Alumni and their alma mater: a partial test of the reformulated model of organizational identification. *J. Organ. Behav.* 13, 103-123. <https://doi.org/10.1002/job.4030130202>
 45. Matten, D. and Moon, J. 2008. “Implicit” and “explicit” CSR: a conceptual framework for a comparative understanding of corporate social

“CSR At Work: How Training, Stability, And Diversity Shape Employee Responses”

- responsibility. *Acad. Manag. Rev.* 33(2), 404-424. <https://doi.org/10.5465/amr.2008.31193458>
46. Miethlich, B. Beliakova, M. Voropaeva, L. Ustuzhina, O. & Yurieva, T. 2023. Internal corporate policy: CSR and employee satisfaction. *Empl. Responsib. Rights J.* 35(1), 127-141. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10672-022-09406-5>
47. Pinder, C. C. 2014. *Work motivation in organizational behavior*. Psychology Press, New York, NY, USA. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315734606>
48. Ringle, C. M. Sarstedt, M. Mitchell, R. and Gudergan, S. P. 2020. Partial least squares structural equation modeling in HRM research. *Int. J. Hum. Resour. Manag.* 31(12), 1617-1643. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585192.2017.1416655>
49. Ringle, C. M., Wende, S., and Becker, J.-M. *SmartPLS 4*. Bönningstedt: SmartPLS, <https://www.smartpls.com>
50. Rupp, D. E. and Mallory, D. B. 2015. Corporate social responsibility: psychological, person-centric, and progressing. *Annu. Rev. Organ. Psychol. Organ. Behav.* 2(1), 211-236. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-orgpsych-032414-111505>
51. Sarstedt, M. Ringle, C. M. and Hair, J. F. 2021. Partial least squares structural equation modeling. In: *Handbook of market research*. pp. 587-632. Springer Int. Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-57413-4_15
52. Shen, J. and Zhu, C. 2011. Effects of socially responsible human resource management on employee organizational commitment. *The Int. J. Hum. Resour. Manag.* 22(15), 3020-3035. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585192.2011.599951>
53. Spector, P. E. 1997. *Job satisfaction: application, assessment, causes, and consequences*. Sage Publications. Thousand Oaks, CA, USA. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781452231549>
54. Story, J.S.P. and Castanheira, F. 2019. Corporate social responsibility and employee performance: mediation role of job satisfaction and affective commitment. *Corp. Soc. Responsib. Environ. Manag.* 26, 1361-1370. <https://doi.org/10.1002/csr.1752>
55. Tang, A. D. Luu, T. T. Chen, W. K. and Liu, S. C. 2023. Internal corporate social responsibility and customer-oriented organizational citizenship behavior: the mediating roles of job satisfaction, work-family facilitation, life satisfaction, and the moderating role of organizational tenure. *J. Sustain. Tour.* 32(5), 986-1007. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09669582.2023.2195134>
56. Tsourvakas, G. and Yfantidou, I. 2018. Corporate social responsibility influences employee engagement. *Soc. Responsib. J.* 14(1), 123-137. <https://doi.org/10.1108/SRJ-09-2016-0153>
57. Turker, D. 2009. Measuring corporate social responsibility: a scale development study. *J. Bus. Ethics* 85, 411-427. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-008-9780-6>
58. Zhou, Z. Luo, B. N., and Tang, T. L. P. 2017. Corporate social responsibility excites ‘exponential’ positive employee engagement: The Matthew effect in CSR and sustainable policy. *Corp. Soc. Responsibility. Environ. Manag.* 25(4), 339-354. <https://doi.org/10.1002/csr.1464>